

Improving temperature tracking control for solar collector fields based on reference feedforward

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Abstract—Improving temperature reference tracking in solar collector fields is essential for enhancing the performance of solar thermal plants. Conventional control strategies are usually employed as static reference feedforwards to reduce rise time when reference changes occur. Nevertheless, strict performance requirements may demand precise control behavior that classical reference feedforwards cannot deliver. Therefore, from theoretical analysis, this work proposes two different control strategies based on reference feedforward structure to accomplish a low rise time and avoid producing overshoot for temperature reference tracking, namely, a lead-lag and a nonlinear reference feedforward. The structures are studied for suitable implementation, assuming an adaptive control framework to keep the same control performance under different operating conditions. Simulation experiments are developed to investigate and compare the proposed strategies with the conventional static feedforward with and without a reference filter. Furthermore, the proposed strategies are successfully tested in an actual solar plant AQUASOL-II, located in the Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA) in Almería, Spain. The promising results have concluded that the lead-lag and nonlinear reference feedforward associated with the adaptive structure have attended the proposed control requirements of low rise time and no overshoot. Moreover, the results have demonstrated the compromise between the lead-lag and the nonlinear controller, where the final choice should be made as a trade-off between performance and control effort.

Index Terms—Reference feedforward, Solar energy, PID controller, Reference tracking

I. INTRODUCTION

EFFORTS to enhance solar thermal systems efficiency rely mainly on adequately controlling solar collector fields' outlet temperature. The solar collectors are in charge of absorbing the solar irradiance energy and delivering it to the load system as thermal power at a specified temperature and Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF, or working fluid) flow criteria. The

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challenges involved in controlling this system are numerous. In the first place, solar collector fields depict particular nonlinear dynamics, and, in addition, they are constantly disturbed by unforeseen meteorological variables, one of which is the primary energy source, that is, the solar irradiance. The second point is that the system operation is intermittent due to the nature of solar irradiance, which requires daily efforts to restart the process to reach operating conditions. This first portrayed issue is related to the regulatory control scenario and the second matter concerns the reference tracking case.

Although the employment of accumulation tanks and auxiliary energy systems contributes to enlarging thermal solar plants operating hours [1], the solar collector field operation persists in being discontinuous, which still requires reference tracking control to restore its operating conditions [2]. Moreover, the system demand may vary according to energy consumption, and changes in the solar collector fields' outlet temperature may be necessary. Furthermore, not only achieving the reference temperature is essential, but the manner it is done is also a crucial criterion. Employing a slow response of the control systems for temperature reference changes may generate waste of resources and, consequently, efficiency losses. On the other hand, fast control actions may produce an overshoot response, which can be harmful to the demand system and even be counterproductive overall. For instance, solar-powered Membrane Distillation (MD) and absorption machines have a slight operating temperature range where the upper boundary violation is critical as it can cause the system to shut down for security specifications and waste energy to restart the operation [3], [4]. This trade-off in the case of reference tracking in solar collector fields is an intriguing control concern.

Even though Nonlinear Model Predictive Controller (NMPC) is one of the most recommended strategies for controlling solar collector fields [5], these control approaches still lack systematic techniques to dictate the attributes of the system's closed-loop dynamics by a prior design, for instance, rise time, percentage of overshoot and settling time. These issues are often addressed within the lower control layers by employing classical Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers [6]–[8]. In particular, the reference tracking design has been presented in several solutions detailed in the literature, either regarding more complex structures, such as Reference Governor [9], [10] and Model Reference [11], [12], or more straightforward frameworks, as Two-Degree-of-Freedom (2DoF) PID controllers [13]. As seen, although

several efforts have been made on this topic, with regard to solar collector field control applications, temperature tracking cases are largely handled with feedforward (FF) reference structures, in which the steady-state gain is calculated using the static models of the plant [14]. Furthermore, these structures have also been improved by adding a reference filter to obtain smooth control signal increments [15].

Including static reference FF in the control structure is challenging in what concerns the tracking performance. This approach accelerates the system response to the reference changing in a certain way that causes an overshoot response due to the feedback (FB) control dynamic. An alternative is to add a dynamic reference FF lead-lag structure, in which the inversion of the system dynamics and the desired output function can fulfill the reference tracking requirements [16]. This method proved to be effective at the cost of producing a high peak control signal due to lead-lag dynamics. Thus, in [17], the author circumscribes this issue by proposing a nonlinear FF structure based on suitable static gains. This solution is pertinent mainly when final actuators operate close to saturation and the control requires fast reference changes. It is noteworthy that the FF solution is very advantageous in practical scenarios since this structure can be included in the control scheme without necessarily rearranging and retuning the central FB controller. Therefore, the reference tracking case is treated separately, and the conventional PID controller is left in charge of dealing with process uncertainties and disturbance rejection.

Therefore, based on the solar thermal field context and control approaches mentioned earlier, this work proposes to improve the reference tracking case for solar collector fields by employing reference FF structures. The motivation is based on practical scenarios, wherein FF structures are still widely used in these facilities due to their straightforward implementation, and easy tuning [14], [18]. Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that the main advantage of using reference FF structures is that this approach dictates the reference tracking dynamics independently of the main FB controller, and therefore the regulation and servo control performances are decoupled. The work presents a comprehensive investigation of the main concerns of the overshoot response caused by the static gain FF with and without a reference filter. Consequently, two convenient alternatives, a Lead-Lag FF (LLFF) [16], and a Nonlinear FF (NLFF) [17] are proposed. These two approaches are compared to classical FF structures employed in these kinds of systems, namely, static FF and static FF plus reference filter [14]. An extensive simulation study is performed to examine the capabilities of each technique to be implemented in the AQUASOL-II solar facility located at the Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), considering the nonlinear solar collector field model in a trustworthy simulation environment. Hence, a PI controller associated with disturbance FF is considered in the control design, in which the nonlinear system dynamic is addressed by an adaptive structure that uses the linearized system model to adjust the controller parameters online. Finally, the proposed lead-lag and nonlinear FF approaches are applied in the real solar plant, and the main performance indices, such as reference error and

control effort, are investigated.

It is noteworthy that, although the proposed solutions refer to classical studied techniques, the LLFF and NLFF approaches have not yet been implemented for controlling solar collector fields nor the analytic investigation of static feedforward regarding overshoot and rise time trade-off criteria [5], [7], [14], [16], [19], which strengthens the practical and theoretical contributions of this work. Furthermore, the adaptive form of the proposed control schemes (LLFF and NLFF) is an attractive and suitable solution to address the system nonlinearities with effortless computational processing [20], ensuring the removal of the overshoot response under different operating conditions and achieving the desired reference tracking in the control of solar collector fields.

This paper is divided as follows: Section II details analytically the static FF issues concerning the reference tracking overshoot response and presents both the lead-lag and the nonlinear FF proposals. Section III presents the simulation results considering the AQUASOL-II systems description and modeling. In Section IV, the actual results of LLFF and NLFF implementation are presented. Finally, Section V details the final considerations.

II. REFERENCE FEEDFORWARD APPROACHES

In this section, the four reference feedforward approaches are introduced. The main focus is to add FF structures and keep the same FB controller tuning in order to improve the reference following case and remove the overshoot response. The general control scheme of all strategies is depicted in the block diagram in Fig. 1, wherein the block $FF_r(s)$ represents the reference FF structure, and $F_r(s)$ the reference filter, in which their structures are suited for each control approach.

Fig. 1. Reference feedforward control scheme.

The block $C(s)$ and $P(s)$ are formulated as commonly found in industry, namely, a PI controller (in the ideal form) and a First Order plus Dead-Time (FOPDT) process, respectively. The representation in the frequency-domain (s) of these blocks is defined as follows:

$$C(s) = K_p \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_i \cdot s} \right) \quad P(s) = \frac{K}{\tau \cdot s + 1} \cdot e^{-L \cdot s} \quad (1)$$

in which K_p is the proportional gain, T_i the integral time, K the process gain, τ the process time constant, L the process delay, and $Y_r(s)$ and $Y(s)$ are the reference and the output signals, respectively. For the following analysis, consider the closed-loop transfer function relating the reference and the output signals as:

$$G(s) = \frac{P(s) \cdot FF_r(s) + P(s) \cdot C(s) \cdot F_r(s)}{1 + P(s) \cdot C(s)} \quad (2)$$

A. Reference FF with static gain

For this first analysis, considering $F_r(s) = 1$, $FF_r(s) = K_{ff}$, and also a first-order delay approximation $e^{-Ls} = (1 - Ls)$, the closed-loop transfer function (2) is now defined as:

$$G(s) = \frac{A \cdot s + \omega_n^2}{s^2 + 2 \cdot \zeta \cdot \omega_n \cdot s + \omega_n^2} \cdot e^{-Ls} \quad (3)$$

wherein

$$A = \frac{(K_{ff} + K_p) \cdot K}{\tau - K \cdot K_p \cdot L}, \quad \omega_n^2 = \frac{K \cdot K_p}{(\tau - K \cdot K_p \cdot L) \cdot T_i},$$

$$2 \cdot \zeta \cdot \omega_n = \frac{(1 + K \cdot K_p) \cdot T_i - K \cdot K_p \cdot L}{(\tau - K \cdot K_p \cdot L) \cdot T_i}$$

For the process reference tracking requirements, the purpose is to generate a fast response without producing an overshoot. Therefore, from (3) two concerns can be seen. First, the closed-loop dynamics must not oscillate and be as fast as possible; thus, $\zeta = 1$. Secondly, the zero must be equal to the fastest pole, in which this condition implies the maximum value for K_{ff} . Hence, based on the previous assumptions, the maximum value for K_{ff} is:

$$K_{ff} = \frac{K_p}{T_i \cdot \omega_n} - K_p \quad (4)$$

This tuning is never done since, in practice, $K_{ff} = 1/K$. In addition, assuming conventional tuning methods for K_p and T_i , for example, the Internal Model Controller (IMC) method, K_{ff} would be negative, which presupposes a gain value contrary to the process gain. This solution is counter-intuitive for the feedforward action, as it makes the control loop requires extra and opposite effort from the feedback action to drive the process variable to the reference value.

B. Reference FF with static gain and reference filter

A widely found alternative to reduce overshoot is to add a low-pass filter in the reference signal. In this approach, the reference filter is defined as $F_r = 1/(T_r \cdot s + 1)$, which causes the reference to vary slowly compared to a step change.

The first practical analysis to tune the reference filter regardless of changing the PI controller is to apply the conventional static FF gain, that is, $K_{ff} = 1/K$. By applying this tuning in (2), the closed-loop transfer function is defined as:

$$G(s) = \frac{1}{T_r \cdot s + 1} \cdot \frac{T_r \cdot T_i \cdot s^2 + (1 + K \cdot K_p) \cdot s + K \cdot K_p}{\tau \cdot T_i \cdot s^2 + (1 + K \cdot K_p) \cdot s + K \cdot K_p} \cdot e^{-Ls} \quad (5)$$

By choosing this tuning, a trade-off compromise arises. If $T_r < \tau$, the resulting reference change will generate an overshoot as higher as the difference. On the contrary, if $T_r > \tau$, the response has a lower time constant than the process itself. Also, if $T_r = \tau$, then the process reaches the reference obeying its time constant.

Another practical and analytical approach to tuning the reference filter to eliminate overshoot is to consider the pole-zero cancellation method. In this procedure, as in several widespread industrial methods, for instance, IMC and SIMC [21], $T_i = \tau$. Hence, considering this solution, and choosing also $T_r = \tau$, the closed-loop transfer function is resumed as:

$$G(s) = \frac{\frac{K_{FF} \cdot \tau}{K_p} \cdot s + 1}{\underbrace{\left(\frac{\tau - K \cdot K_p \cdot L}{K \cdot K_p} \cdot s + 1 \right)}_{\lambda} (\tau \cdot s + 1)} \cdot e^{-Ls} \quad (6)$$

in which λ is the desired closed-loop dynamic defined by design.

This approach leaves the reference tracking requirements in charge of the $FF_r(s)$ tuning. Thus, for the lowest rise time without overshoot, considering that the PI tuning generates a closed-loop response faster than the process dynamics, the best tuning is $K_{ff} = K_p$. Any value greater than K_p will generate an overshoot, while the opposite will produce a higher rise time.

Moreover, a heuristic tuning method is used to adjust the reference filter and not generate an overshoot, as detailed in [16]. By studying the process response, employing $T_r = t_p \cdot \sqrt{M^2 - 1}$, wherein M is the magnitude of the overshoot and t_p the time of the peak, the reference filter is capable of eliminating the overshoot.

Nevertheless, as can be seen from the proposed tuning methods, the static gain of the FF structure plus the reference filter still lacks degrees of freedom to obtain a faster response without producing overshoot, which makes it necessary to change the PI controller tuning in order to achieve the desired controller performance.

C. Lead-Lag Feedforward structure

In the previously presented approaches, the FF structures were determined only by a static gain. A significant improvement of this scenario can be achieved by adding a stable inversion structure related to the reference filter and the process dynamic to the FF action. This structure, namely, lead-lag, can determine the desired closed-loop response for the reference changes only by adjusting the time constant of the reference filter. As a result, the control performance for set-point change can be defined a priori without altering the internal PI controller.

To analyze this case, consider the following transfer functions

$$FF_r(s) = \frac{1}{K} \cdot \frac{\tau \cdot s + 1}{T_r \cdot s + 1}, \quad F_r = \frac{1}{T_r \cdot s + 1} \quad (7)$$

Replacing (7) in (2), the resulting closed-loop transfer function is $G(s) = e^{-Ls} / (T_r \cdot s + 1)$. This new structure is promising since it attends to all the presented control requirements for the solar collector fields. In addition, it is worth mentioning that the main advantage of this method is leaving the PI controller to deal with disturbance rejection and possible miss-matches scenarios, allowing the designer to tune

the PI according to these other requirements. Nevertheless, if the inversion dynamic is non-causal, the FF structure will consider only the causal part, which compromises the closed-loop performance. In addition, this action generates a higher control signal peak, which can be undesirable due to actuators' saturation.

D. Nonlinear Feedforward

As presented in [17], an ingenious solution to overcome the actuator saturation issues is to adopt a nonlinear feedforward structure. The central aspect is to employ a switching scheme for the feedforward signal. In this solution, the FF block output is chosen as follows:

$$u_{ff}(t) = \begin{cases} \bar{u}_{ff}, & \text{if } t < t_{cut} \\ \frac{1}{K}, & \text{if } t \geq t_{cut} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

with

$$\bar{u}_{ff} = \frac{1/K}{1 - e^{-t_{cut}/\tau}},$$

and where t_{cut} is the time designed for the process to reach the reference, being $u_{ff}(t)$ the FF signal. In addition, the reference filter is designed as:

$$F_r(s) = \frac{K \cdot \bar{u}_{ff}}{\tau \cdot s + 1} \cdot e^{-L \cdot s} \quad (9)$$

By applying this solution, the FF action delivers two piecewise constant values without producing a high peak, as it occurs in the lead-lag structure, which is beneficial for avoiding the actuators' saturation. Moreover, the rise time can be easily defined by adjusting just one parameter, the transition time t_{cut} . As detailed in [17], the design of t_{cut} is crucial for handling the trade-off between performance, robustness, and control activity. Nevertheless, this approach presents significant concerns for implementation. First, this nonlinear solution requires real-time measurements, which can be troubled in real case scenarios. Secondly, since the nonlinear term is dependent on the elapsed time, adaptively applying this structure is not trivial, and it may lead to poor performance of the NLFF.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

This sections aims to summarize the main concerns and results about the FF structures performance presented previously for the problem of reference changes in solar collector field systems. The four control structures are implemented to control the AQUASOL-II solar collector field in a validated and trustworthy simulation environment. The first stage is to present the nonlinear AQUASOL-II model. Then, the controllers are implemented in a linearized operating point of the plant. Lastly, the presented controllers are tested considering actual operating day data in a nonlinear simulation scenario.

A. AQUASOL-II solar collector field model

The AQUASOL-II plant is located at PSA, a dependency of the Spanish Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT). The AQUASOL-II solar field includes 60 flat-plate collectors in the primary circuit; however, in this study, only one loop of the solar collector field, consisting of four sets of five flat-plate collectors (20 in total), is used. Fig. 2 describes the AQUASOL-II solar collector field system.

Fig. 2. First loop of the AQUASOL-II solar field

For this study, the solar collector field model is proposed as a simplified lumped-parameter, in which it is possible to formulate a linearized representation straightforwardly. In addition, this type of model presents a high fidelity representation and a satisfactory performance concerning computational cost, which is quite suitable for control simulation purposes. Equation (10) depicts the AQUASOL-II solar collector model.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dT_{sc,o}(t)}{dt} = & \frac{\beta}{\rho \cdot C_p \cdot A_{sc}} \cdot I(t - d_I) \\ & - \frac{H}{\rho \cdot C_p \cdot A_{sc} \cdot L_{eq}} \cdot (T_{sc,m}(t) - T_a(t)) \\ & - \frac{q(t - d_q)}{A_{sc} \cdot c_f} \cdot \frac{T_{sc,o}(t) - T_{sc,in}(t - d_{T_{in}})}{L_{eq}} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

wherein $T_{sc,o}(t)$ [°C] is the outlet temperature, $T_{sc,in}(t)$ [°C] the inlet temperature, $I(t)$ [W/m²] the solar irradiance, $T_a(t)$ [°C] the ambient temperature $T_{sc,m}(t)$ is the mean between the inlet and outlet temperature, $T_{sc,m}(t) = (T_{sc,o}(t) + T_{sc,in}(t - d_{T_{in}}))/2$. In addition, the delay time $d_{T_{in}}$ is associated with the inlet temperature, d_q is associated with the water flow rate, and d_I associated to the apparent delay of the irradiance [22]. The water flow $q(t)$ [L/min] is the manipulated variable, while $T_{sc,o}(t)$ is the controlled variable. The model validation is conducted using two days of empirical tests in the AQUASOL-II. The procedure applied is an optimization method to minimize the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the plant outlet temperature and the model $T_{sc,o}(t)$ variable

TABLE I

MODEL PARAMETERS DESCRIPTION FOR THE SOLAR COLLECTOR FIELD. THE TERMS DENOTED WITH * WERE FOUND BY THE OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE

Parameter	Description	Unit
A_{sc}	Solar collector pipe cross-section area	$7.85 \cdot 10^{-5}$ [m ²]
c_f	Conversion factor (number of parallel modules and unit conversion)	$12 \cdot 10^6$ [s·L/(min·m ³)]
C_p	Specific heat capacity of water	4190 [J/(kg·°C)]
H^*	Global heat losses coefficient	0.9118 [J/(s·°C)]
L_{eq}	Equivalent absorber tube length	1.94 [m]
β^*	Irradiance model parameter	0.0697 [m]
ρ	Water density	975 [kg/m ³]
$d_{T_{in}}^*$	$T_{sc,in}(t)$ delay	57 [s]
d_q^*	$q(t)$ delay	52 [s]
d_I^*	$I(t)$ delay	53 [s]

by calibrating parameters β , H , $d_{T_{in}}$, d_q , and d_I . The experiment is conducted over a wide range of plant operation, and although the transport delays can vary depending on the water flow [14], the delays are calculated as a mean value during the tests without compromising the model validation. The parameter values and their descriptions are detailed in Table I.

B. FF implementation in a linearized plant operation

In this stage, the four FF control schemes are implemented considering the linearized model of the plant at the following operating point: $\bar{I} = 858.1$ W/m², $\bar{T}_a = 18.3$ °C, $\bar{T}_{sc,in} = 56.7$ °C, $\bar{q} = 8.1$ L/min and $\bar{T}_{sc,o} = 83.0$ °C, in which the notation \bar{x} makes mention of the variable at the operating point. The achieved linearized model derived from (10) is depicted as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{sc,o}(s) = & \frac{1}{\underbrace{193.30}_{K_I} \cdot s + 1} \cdot \underbrace{(-2.78)}_{K_q} \cdot e^{-52s} \cdot q(s) \\
 & + \underbrace{0.0420}_{K_I} \cdot e^{-53s} \cdot I(s) + \underbrace{0.7178}_{K_{T_{sc,in}}} \cdot e^{-57s} \cdot T_{sc,in}(s) \quad (11) \\
 & - \underbrace{0.2822}_{K_{T_a}} \cdot T_a(s)
 \end{aligned}$$

in which τ is the process time constant, and K_q , K_I , $K_{T_{sc,in}}$ and K_{T_a} are the gains related to the water flow, solar irradiance, inlet and ambient temperatures, respectively.

The goal is to evaluate the controllers' performances considering the overall controller effort, the FF and FB effort, separately, and the temperature error. In this simulation, the PI tuning is based on the IMC method for all the tests, wherein $T_i = \tau$, $K_p = T_i / (K \cdot (\lambda + L))$ and $\lambda = 0.8 \cdot \tau$ [21]. The four FF are adjusted as follows:

- FF static gain (FF1):

$$FF_r = \frac{1}{K_q}$$

- FF static gain + Ref. Filter (FF2):

$$FF_r = \frac{1}{K_q}, F_r = \frac{1}{0.5 \cdot \tau \cdot s + 1}$$

- Lead-lag FF (LLFF):

$$FF_r = \frac{1}{K_q} \cdot \frac{\tau \cdot s + 1}{\frac{0.8 \cdot \tau}{4} \cdot s + 1}, F_r = \frac{1}{\frac{0.8 \cdot \tau}{4} \cdot s + 1}$$

- Nonlinear FF (NLFF):

$$t_{cut} = 0.8 \cdot \tau$$

Note that the LLFF and NLFF tuning makes it possible to dictate the rise time, and thus, the FF controllers are tuned to achieve similar performance. Fig. 3 details the temperature and the water flow evolution, and Fig. 4 the controller signals. In this study, the disturbances are kept constant throughout the simulation aiming to investigate only the tracking control performances. In addition, Table II presents the performance indices as the Sum of Control Increments (SCI), Mean Square Error (MSE, between the desired reference and the output), Sum of Absolute Control signal (SAU), and Percentage of Overshoot (POV).

Fig. 3. Temperature and water flow for the linearized model simulation.

TABLE II

PERFORMANCE INDICES FOR THE LINEAR MODEL SIMULATION.

	MSE (10 ²)	SCI	SCI _{PI}	SCI _{FF}	SAU (10 ⁴)	POV
NLFF	8.25	1.99	0	1.99	1.41	0
LLFF	6.26	6.80	0	6.80	1.44	0
FF2	11.69	1.32	0.56	0.76	1.37	0.12
FF1	8.79	3.17	2.41	0.76	1.37	0.50

As can be observed, this preliminary results is in line with the analysis presented in Section II. The FF_r structure with static gain generates an overshoot that can be reduced

Fig. 4. PI and FF output signals for the linearized model simulation

by applying a reference filter. Nevertheless, the rise time specification is compromised, demonstrating that the static gain approach can not solve the trade-off between lower rise time and eliminating the overshoot. Employing a lead-lag structure makes it possible to reduce the rise time and not generating overshoot, but at the cost of producing a high peak on the control signal. Furthermore, improved performance is achieved using the NLFF, wherein the piece-wise gain removes the peak of the FF controller. Moreover, as can be seen from Table II, both the LLFF and the NLFF guarantee higher reference tracking performance without demanding any effort from the FB controller, while the static gain approaches still use the internal PI controller to achieve the desired reference.

Regarding the control effort indices, it is possible to notice that the NLFF overcomes the LLFF, in which the control sign has much fewer increments for the nonlinear approach, about 70% less. However, the ideal scenario presented is misleading since the control performance is excellent considering the linear case in a simulated environment. Assuming the nonlinear context, a more trustworthy test must be done, as encountered in the actual plant.

C. Nonlinear model control

Aiming to provide relevant results concerning the accurate implementation, the four FF controllers are employed to control the simulated nonlinear model. In this scenario, the nonlinear solar collector field model is used, associated with two more subsystems, an accumulation tank, and a heater exchanger, in order to reproduce a stable inlet temperature profile and a load system, as occurs in the actual AQUASOL-II plant. Fig. 5 represents the simulated system's configuration.

Concerning the controller framework, since the main objective is to investigate the reference tracking case, three disturbance FF are employed to reduce the effects of the irradiance, inlet, and ambient temperatures over the controlled output temperature. Also, an anti-windup method based on the back-calculation scheme is proposed to overcome integral computation issues due to the actuator limits. Furthermore, an extra adaptive control structure is employed to ensure that the specific FF control tuning is according to the system operating point and improve the FF reference tracking performance. From (11), by applying the Taylor series method, truncated in the first term, the linear model parameters are dependent on

Fig. 5. AQUASOL-II facility simulation configuration.

the water flow, the inlet and outlet temperatures, as detailed in (12). The adaptive block computes the new linearized process parameters and updates all the controllers tuning. The disturbance FF structures are designed as presented in (13) and the complete control structure is detailed in Fig. 6.

$$K_q = \frac{-\frac{C_p \rho}{c_f L} (\bar{T}_{sc,o} - \bar{T}_{sc,i})}{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} + \frac{H}{2L} \right]} \quad K_I = \frac{\beta}{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} + \frac{H}{2L} \right]}$$

$$K_{T_{sc,in}} = \frac{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} - \frac{H}{2L} \right]}{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} + \frac{H}{2L} \right]} \quad K_{T_a} = \frac{\frac{H}{L}}{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} + \frac{H}{2L} \right]} \quad (12)$$

$$\tau = \frac{\rho C_p A_{sc}}{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} + \frac{H}{2L} \right]}$$

$$FF_I = -\frac{K_I}{K_q} \cdot e^{-(d_I + d_q) \cdot s}, \quad FF_{T_a} = -\frac{K_{T_a}}{K_q}, \quad (13)$$

$$FF_{T_{sc,in}} = -\frac{K_{T_{sc,in}}}{K_q} \cdot e^{-(d_{T_{sc,in}} + d_q) \cdot s}$$

Fig. 6. AQUASOL-II adaptive control scheme.

The adaptive control law is employed given the following rules: (i) for the disturbance FF structures, since these blocks

are only static gains, their values are calculated at each sample time, $T_s = 1$ s, (ii) for the FF1, FF2, LLFF, and PI controllers, the parameters are calculated using a moving average of 20 s of the water flow variable, aiming to avoid sudden changes, (iii) for the NLFF, since this block calculates the gain switch instant based on the elapsed time, the adaptive control updates this block only when a reference change occurs, and it is not revised until another set-point alteration is applied.

Actual data from the AQUASOL-II plant on January 17, 2022, are used as input data. In the simulated scenario, the four adaptive controllers proposed in Section II are simulated in order to compare the effects of employing the adaptive reference FF structure. During four simulated hours, reference changes are made from 10.5 h to 14.5 h considering 1 °C and 1.5 °C amplitudes, both positive and negative. In addition, a more substantial external disturbance is virtually induced at 12.5 h in the inlet temperature in order to observe the effect of the disturbance on the FF structures.

Regarding the controllers set-up, the same PI tuning is employed for all controllers, and the FF_r and PI structures are tuned as detailed in Section II. The anti-windup parameter is chosen as $T_{wp} = \sqrt{T_i}$. Fig. 7 presents the meteorological and the inlet temperature variables. Moreover, Fig. 8 and 9 depict the temperature evolution during the operating period of the day and the controller signals, and Fig. 10 shows the identified linear process parameters throughout the operating period of the simulation.

Fig. 7. Meteorological data on day January 17, 2022, and inlet temperature variable.

Aiming to illustrate the effect of the adaptive control block, two controllers are compared: the adaptive LLFF (as detailed previously) and a simple LLFF (s-LLFF), by using a single tuning considering the starting of the plant operation, in which the variables states are: $\bar{I} = 742.03$ W/m², $\bar{T}_a = 21.78$ °C, $\bar{T}_{sc,in} = 54.12$ °C, $\bar{q} = 7.5$ L/min and $\bar{T}_{sc,o} = 77.22$ °C. Fig. 11 depicts the controlled variable for each strategy.

Accordingly, as a final comparison, a miss-match scenario is presented. The solar collector field is simulated with uncertainties, imposing an unfavorable scenario for the controllers. Therefore, the parameters β and H of the simulated plant model are chosen 20 % higher than those used in the linearized model by controllers. Moreover, parameter d_q is selected as 63 s for the simulated plant, while the control structures are kept as depicted in Table I. Fig. 12 and 13 present the results of the LLFF and NLFF for the uncertainty scenario, namely,

un-LLFF and un-NLFF.

Finally, the performance indices are used to examine the proposed control strategies quantitatively. Table III present the MSE, SAU, SIC, and POV for all strategies.

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE INDICES FOR THE NONLINEAR MODEL SIMULATION.

	MSE (10 ²)	SCI	SCI _{PI}	SCI _{FF_r}	SAU (10 ⁴)	POV
NLFF	7.10	20.52	0.90	8.29	1.81	0.09
LLFF	5.16	46.50	2.10	32.31	2.48	0.06
s-LLFF	5.18	48.46	2.93	34.77	2.83	0.33
FF2	8.93	17.20	3.65	4.72	2.46	0.09
FF1	8.55	29.56	11.89	5.12	2.48	0.77
un-LLFF	5.70	58.19	11.37	32.72	1.02	0.78
un-NLFF	9.55	68.23	30.64	8.29	1.81	2.39

D. Results Discussion

In the first place, it must be noted that the proposed control structure, including the adaptive and the disturbance FF structures are well implemented and designed. The three disturbances FF accounted for only static gain and delays. However, they can accurately minimize the effects of the irradiance, inlet, and ambient temperatures, even though the ambient temperature FF is designed only with the causal part of the invertible dynamic. This result is especially seen in the inlet temperature disturbance at 12.5 h, in which a step-change occurs, and the $FF_{T_{sc,in}}$ strategy was able to reject it. In addition, from Fig. 11 and Table III it can be observed that the adaptive design of the control strategy is valuable for the nonlinear system application. From Fig. 11, it can be seen that both the LLFF and the s-LLFF perform very similarly for the first two reference changes. However, when the system conditions move away from the linearized operating point, the s-LLFF starts to perform unsatisfactorily (see Table III), leading to an overshoot response eventually. It is clear that, for the proposed reference tracking requirements, it is essential to consider the adaptive framework concerning the implementation of the proposed control strategy in a nonlinear system.

Furthermore, in what concerns the studied reference FF strategies, the results are consistent and reproduce the linear model simulation scenario. Once again, both static gain approaches, FF1 and FF2, still perform poorly for set-point changes, even when the adaptive strategy is assessed, as can be noted on the indices in Table III. Again, the NLFF and LLFF are the most promising strategies, showing a low rise time with almost zero overshoot. It is noteworthy that when both strategies employed with the adaptive formulation almost reproduce the linear simulation, wherein the PI is only used for minor corrections due to miss-match scenarios that slightly occur, presenting small SIC_{PI} indices. Nevertheless, as is already expected, the LLFF still demonstrates a higher FF signal peak, which can be inappropriate due to the actuator limitations. Comparing the LLFF with the NLFF from Table III, it can be noted that the reduction of 27.3% on the MSE index comes with an increase of almost 74% of the FF_r increments, which outlines the primary trade-off matter of the presented approaches.

Fig. 8. Outlet temperature and water flow for FF controllers comparison.

Fig. 9. PI and FF_r signals for controllers comparison - values related to the deviation variable of the water flow steady-state $\bar{q} = 7.5$ L/min

Finally, the last uncertainty scenario must be highlighted. For the presented nonlinear system with uncertainty model parameters, the NLFF conducts very poorly, mainly for negative variations in the reference. When an inaccurate gain is calculated for the first piece-wise signal and there is mismatch on the delay of the reference filter, the NLFF generates a strong disturbance during t_{cut} s, which is promptly handled by the internal PI controller. As seen in the proposed simulation,

displayed in Fig. 12, it may even generate strong oscillations in the controlled variable. On the other hand, although the same inaccuracy affects the LLFF, the reference FF's effect is shorter than the NLFF, which may lead to a faster response by the internal controller to correct the inappropriate reference FF signal. Consequently, for the proposed case study of the solar collector field, which is a highly nonlinear multidisturbed and delayed system, based on the presented results in Table III,

Fig. 10. Model linear parameters online identified by the adaptive control structure.

Fig. 11. Outlet temperature and water flow for LLFF comparison on the adaptive formulation.

Fig. 12. Outlet temperature and water flow for the uncertainty scenario of the un-FLL and un-NLFF.

Fig. 13. PI and FF_r signals for un-FLL and un-NLFF comparison - values related to the deviation variable of the water flow steady-state $\bar{q} = 7.5$ L/min.

the NLFF has been verified to be more sensitive to modeling uncertainties than the LLFF strategy.

To summarize the main capabilities of the proposed strategies and serve as performance guidelines, Table IV condenses the control attributes based on the presented analysis and results.

TABLE IV

RESUME TABLE OF THE MAIN CAPABILITIES OF THE REFERENCE FF STRUCTURES.

	FF1	FF2	LLFF	NLFF
Overshoot	High	Medium	None	None
Rise time	High	Low	High	High
Internal FB effort	High	Medium	None	None
Reference FF effort	Low	Low	High	Medium
Total control effort	Medium	Medium	High	Low
Adaptive capabilities	High	High	Medium	Medium
Robustness	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low

Therefore, based on the optimistic results of the NLFF and LLFF regarding the achievements of the reference tracking scenario for the solar collector fields' requirements, these two control strategies were tested in the actual AQUASOL-II.

IV. CONTROLLING THE AQUASOL-II PLANT

After investigating the main concerns of the proposed reference FF strategies, the LLFF and the NLFF approaches are implemented in the AQUASOL-II solar plant using the adaptive control structures depicted in Fig. 6 and the control tuning presented in Section III. The experiments were conducted on May 16, 2022, for the FLL, and on May 18, 2022, for the NLFF, wherein in both scenarios, the meteorologic conditions were ideal for the reference tracking experiment, presenting sunny days, as presented in Fig. 14. Both strategies have been proven by making mostly positive variations of the outlet temperature reference to reach a wide temperature operating range (58 - 74 °C) and keep the water flow within its limits, which are 5.4 L/min and 14.6 L/min. During the experiment, the AQUASOL-II subsystem was similar to that used in the simulation test, only differing in the accumulation tank, in which, in the actual experiment, an air cooler is used to keep the inlet temperature low and controlled.

Fig. 14. Meteo conditions for AQUASOL-II experiments on days May 16, 2022 and May 18, 2022.

As detailed in Fig 15, the FFL has no struggles in following the temperature changes throughout the operating

Fig. 15. Outlet temperature and water flow for the LLFF test in AQUASOL-II plant on May 16, 2022.

Fig. 16. Outlet temperature and water flow for the NLFF test in AQUASOL-II plant on May 18, 2022.

range and keeping the desired control requirements, which are a fast rise time and no overshoot. Moreover, following the simulation results, the strategy produced a high control signal peak, contributing to a high control effort. Likewise, Fig. 16 presents the NLFF. In this experiment, after a preliminary test, the control strategy was adjusted, considering particular changeovers that had occurred in the plant configuration, which led to new values of d_q , β , and H . After readjusting the model parameters, the control behavior presented by the nonlinear strategy follows the simulation results, in which no overshoot is produced as the control presented a less abrupt dynamic of the water flow compared to the LLFF.

The controllers' responses can be compared in Fig. 17, in which the PI and the FF_r signals are presented. As confirmed in the simulation results, the NLFF is more sensitive to modeling errors than the LLFF. Consequently, the NLFF required more action of the PI controller in the experimental test when compared to the LLFF, since the nonlinear solar collector field model used can be very susceptible to parameter uncertainties. A quantitative comparison can be observed in Table V, in which now the performance indices are presented per sample (which is 1 s). Mirroring the simulation results, the FF_r effort is higher for the LLFF approach and has a lower MSE. In addition, the PI effort for the NLFF has also increased, demonstrating the need to use the internal controller more to compensate for model uncertainties.

Finally, it must be noteworthy that the proposed adaptive controllers have shown to be notably promising, simple to implement, and reasonably practical, as both controllers man-

Fig. 17. PI and FF_r signal for the FFL and NLFF control strategies prove in the AQUASOL-II plant - values related to the deviation variable of the water flow steady-state $\bar{q} = 11.8$ L/min for the FFL and $\bar{q} = 10.3$ L/min for the NLFF.

TABLE V

PERFORMANCE INDICES FOR THE AQUASOL-II TESTS.

	MSE (10^2)	SCI (10^3)	SCI _{PI} (10^3)	SCI _{FF_r}	POV
NLFF	40.01	7.60	2.60	1.10	0.42
LLFF	20.98	11.20	2.40	8.10	0.20

aged to maintain almost the same performance for different operating points of the nonlinear plant, meeting the desired performance requirements in a wide operating range.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Several reference FF are proposed concerning specific performance requirements for solar thermal plant control. In particular, based on mathematical analysis, conventional reference control strategies, mainly based on static gain, have demonstrated to not dispose of sufficient degrees of freedom to deliver low rise time and no overshoot without modifying the predefined internal control tuning. Consequently, this work has proposed two advantageous reference FF control schemes considering the control of solar collector fields, the LLFF and the NLFF.

As the primary outcomes, both strategies can be predefined based on the plant model to achieve the desired performance without producing any overshoot and readjusting the internal controller. The advantage is precise, since it can be implemented over the primary and already formulated controller, and it achieves lower rise time, permitting the internal controller to deal only with disturbance and uncertainties scenarios. The choice between the LLFF and the NLFF must always be made by weighing the trade-off between higher control signal effort and lower output error (LLFF) or lower control effort and less robust strategy (NLFF). In addition, considering the practical scenario investigated, the solar collector field, the presented adaptive strategy has demonstrated to keep the same performance in different operating conditions even though the controlled system is highly nonlinear regarding the controlled and manipulated variables.

The control investigation is concluded by successfully applying the proposed LLFF and NLFF in the AQUASOL-II facility, wherein the achieved control performance is strictly similar to the simulation results. As demonstrated by the simulated and the actual experiments, the proposed reference

FF is advantageous in what concerns solar collector field control requirements. Moreover, the proposed adaptive strategies are easily and practically implemented with evident control performance improvements.

Significant concerns should be made considering the LLFF strategy, as this controller is only advantageous when invertible dynamics are possible, which on the contrary, the FF performance is compromised. Furthermore, as evidenced in the simulation results, the NLFF is especially susceptible to modeling uncertainties, and further investigation is demanded to improve this strategy performance. Future works, in addition, consist of evaluating the presented control strategies associated with predictive control strategies as internal controllers aiming to improve robustness and simplify the adaptive control structure using NMPC approaches.

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